

Exploring the Gender Gap in Technology Access and Its Impact on Academic and Career Readiness Among Undergraduate Students in Bangladesh

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Abstract

This study investigates the gender disparities in technology access among undergraduate students in Bangladesh and examines how these disparities influence academic engagement and career preparedness. Using a series of chi-square tests and cross-tabulation analyses, the research highlights significant differences in the types of technology used, methods of acquisition, and frequency of technology use between male and female students. The findings reveal that male students generally have greater access to personal computers, more financial autonomy, and higher engagement with technology for academic purposes. In contrast, female students face barriers such as limited access to multiple devices, a reliance on family support, and household responsibilities, which hinder their ability to fully utilize educational technology. The study also shows that these disparities contribute to differences in academic performance, career confidence, and participation in career-enhancing activities such as internships and part-time jobs. These results suggest that gender-based technological inequalities in Bangladesh are a significant factor in reinforcing broader socio-economic and educational inequities. The paper concludes by calling for targeted policy interventions to improve technology access for female students, including subsidized device programs and digital literacy initiatives, in order to promote greater academic and career readiness across gender lines.

Keywords: Gender gap, Digital Divide, Technology Usage for Education, Academic Preparation, Career Preparation

1. Introduction

In recent years, the gender gap in education has garnered significant attention, particularly in developing countries like Bangladesh, where societal norms and economic factors often

influence access to educational opportunities. (Kuteesa et al., 2024) (N. Islam & Jirattikorn, 2024). While considerable progress has been made in reducing this gap, disparities still exist, especially when examining how these differences impact future career prospects. The transition from education to employment is crucial for economic development, and any inequality in this area can have long-lasting effects on the job market and overall societal progress. (Moniruzzaman & Emran, 2021)

Undergraduate students, as future professionals, represent a critical group to study in understanding how the gender gap in education translates into job market preparedness. The challenges faced by female students, particularly in accessing technology, balancing academic and household responsibilities, and poor engagement with extracurricular activities, often hinder their full participation in the job market (Pulatovna, 2024) (Jamatia, 2023). Additionally, the underrepresentation of women in STEM fields, where employment opportunities are more abundant and financially rewarding, further exacerbates the disparity in career readiness between male and female students (Kuteesa et al., 2024)

In Bangladesh, cultural and societal expectations place a disproportionate burden on female students, affecting their educational experience and career ambitions (Sarkar, 2022). While male students may benefit from greater access to resources and career-building activities, female students often juggle responsibilities that limit their ability to fully engage in academic and professional development (Chan et al., 2023). Understanding these dynamics is crucial for developing strategies to foster a more equitable job market.

This research aims to explore the extent of the gender gap through technology access in education among undergraduate students in Bangladesh and assess how it affects their preparedness for the job market. By examining key factors such as access to technology, academic performance, participation in extracurricular activities, and career aspirations, this study seeks to shed light on the barriers that female students face and provide insights into how these challenges can be addressed to create a more inclusive educational and employment landscape.

2. Literature review

There have been remarkable improvements in women's educational attainments in Bangladesh. Further, female education is found to be positively correlated with their workforce participation, though most women in the workforce are self-employed or employed in low-skill jobs (M. A. Hossain & Tisdell, 2005)

However, recent studies highlight persistent gender disparities in higher education and job preparedness in Bangladesh. Women in STEM face challenges including gender-biased classroom interactions, lack of resources, and limited female role models, leading to imposter

syndrome and career anxiety (Rahman, 2024). While factors like family preferences, job security, and personal interests influence career choices, gender and social class have minimal impact (Siddiky & Akter, 2021). Students recognize the changing job market but lack preparedness for Industry 4.0 challenges (Md. A. Islam, 2022) female has poor access to ICT educational materials and thus gather low technical skills and knowledge than man.(ref need). Despite increased higher education completion rates among women, employment rates have not kept pace. Female students improve intrinsic empowerment but face constraints in instrumental empowerment due to stereotyped subject selection, limited IT competence, lack of relevant job skills, and limited career aspirations (Ahmed & Hyndman-Rizk, 2020). To address these issues, recommendations include improving educational quality, providing career development training, and establishing career guidance services to better align graduates' skills with labor market demands.

Gender disparity in technology access significantly impacts academic preparation and job market readiness. Technology access has been shown to improve educational attainment and reduce academic disparities caused by socioeconomic differences (Alam & Forhad, 2023). The gender-technology access gap is becoming increasingly important in the context of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, affecting education choices, job participation, and business opportunities (Šestić et al., 2020). In Afghanistan, women face significant barriers to technology access, limiting their opportunities for education, employment, and economic empowerment (Nabizada et al., 2024). A study on distance learning students found that female students felt more prepared for their careers when they perceived library resources as accessible and when university-provided technology was reliable (Smith, 2015). These findings highlight the need for targeted interventions to address gender-based technology access disparities and promote equal opportunities in education and the career preparedness.

Access to technology improves academic achievements and reduces educational disparities among Bangladeshi undergraduate students specially those from lower socio-economic backgrounds (Alam & Forhad, 2023). A 1:4 gender ratio in computer science education (STEM) is found in Bangladesh while girls face various social and economic barriers (Tasmin et al., 2019).

Undergraduate students represent a critical population for examining how disparities in technology access between females and males contribute to differences in academic achievement and long-term career outcomes. At this stage of life, students are developing the knowledge, skills, and experiences that shape their future educational and professional trajectories. If male and female students have unequal access to resources such as computers, the internet, or digital learning tools, these disparities may influence their academic performance (Md. T. Hossain et al., 2023). Over time, such imbalances can expand into broader inequalities in career opportunities.

Research has extensively explored the digital divide across genders, focusing on internet usage, digital competencies, selection of STEM subjects, and participation in STEM professions (Mariscal et al., 2019). However, there is limited empirical evidence examining how disparities in technology access influence both academic preparation and career development among Bangladeshi undergraduate students. This gap underscores the importance of exploring whether limited technology access contributes to lower workforce participation among female students relative to their male peers.

Ensuring equal access to technology in education is essential to narrowing the gender gap, as it supports digital literacy and skills development among women. Nevertheless, improved access to technology alone does not guarantee equitable employment outcomes. Broader socio-economic factors—such as gender discrimination and labor market structures—also play a critical role in shaping women’s workforce participation (Valli, 2025).

While technology has the potential to empower women through educational opportunities and by challenging societal norms, substantial barriers remain. These include the persistent digital divide, gender biases in STEM fields, and structural socio-economic obstacles that continue to hinder women’s full participation in the workforce.

3. Research Aim and Objectives

This study aims to assess how the gender gap influences access to technology and how such disparities impact educational outcomes and job market readiness. Undergraduate students have been selected as a representative group of the broader student population in Bangladesh. The objectives are:

The specific objectives of this research are:

- To assess the differences in technology access between male and female students.
- To analyze how disparities in technology access contribute to unequal academic preparation between male and female students.
- To examine the extent to which differences in technology access affect career preparedness across genders.
- To evaluate the impact of gendered household responsibilities on access to technology for educational purposes and subsequent academic and professional development.
- To explore how unequal family support across genders influences access to technology in the context of educational and career preparation.

4. Research Methodology

a. Research Design

This study employs a quantitative, descriptive, cross-sectional research design. The primary objective is to explore the gender gap in technology access and its impact on academic achievement and career readiness among undergraduate students in Bangladesh. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire. Statistical analyses, including cross-tabulation and chi-square tests, were performed using SPSS to examine relationships between the identified variables. This research design enables a systematic examination of gender disparities in technology access, educational advancement, and job market readiness, supported by empirical data and rigorous analysis.

b. Variables

The study is structured around the following variables.

Independent Variables (IV)

Note: Certain variables in this study, such as technology access, may serve as either independent or dependent variables depending on the specific hypothesis being tested. The classification below reflects their role in each corresponding context.

Independent variables are those that hypothetically might influence or affect the dependent variables. In my study following are considered:

- Gender: Male and Female.
- Technology Access related variables : Access to PC , Tech usage for education, Challenges in accessing technology, primary study device, Device acquisition method, If purchased, Reason for device purchase, Access to multiple devices for studies , Device usage time for academic, Impact of device source on tech access.
- Academic Performance related variables : Weekly study hours, Involvement in extra curricular activities, Enrollment in tuition or academic support, Impact of tuition or part time work on academic performance,

In this study, "weekly study hours" were selected as a proxy for academic preparation rather than traditional academic performance measures such as GPA or exam scores. This choice was made considering the evolving educational curriculum in Bangladesh, which undergoes frequent changes often without consistent alignment with expert academic recommendations. As a result, there are growing concerns among academic experts regarding the actual workplace readiness and competency of high-GPA achievers. Therefore, this study emphasizes academic effort over formal grades, based on the rationale that consistent study habits and time investment better reflect a student's genuine preparation and learning process in this context. Weekly study hours were thus considered a more reliable and meaningful indicator of academic engagement for the purposes of this research.

- STEM Extracurricular Activities: Participation in Science clubs or math clubs, Olympiads (Math, Physics, Biology), innovation competitions, robotics teams or coding clubs, workshops on AI, data science or blockchain, science project etc.
- Part-time Employment: Whether students work part-time during their studies.
- Household Responsibilities: Time spent on household chores, caregiving, etc.
- Socioeconomic Status: Family income level, parents' education, etc.
- Geographic Location: Urban vs. rural residency.

Dependent Variables (DV)

Dependent variables are those that are expected to be influenced by the independent variables. Here included:

- Academic Performance related variables : Weekly study hours, Involvement in extracurricular activities, Enrollment in tuition or academic support, Impact of tuition or part time work on academic performance.
- Preparedness for Job Market related variables : Impact of extracurricular activities on job market preparedness, Weekly part time work hours, Part time job or internship experience, Impact of tuition or part time work on job market preparation, Motivation for pursuing tuition or part time job, Confidence in entering job market after graduation,

c. Key Variables to Explore

✓ **Technology Access**

This variable examines whether male students have better access to technology compared to female students and how this disparity influences academic performance and career preparation.

✓ **Household Responsibilities**

This variable focuses on the gendered distribution of household duties, assessing whether female students spend more time on domestic responsibilities than male students, and how this affects their ability to access technology for educational and professional development.

✓ **Part-Time Job or Internship Experience**

This variable explores whether access to technology facilitates involvement in part-time jobs or internships, which are critical in building job-relevant skills and knowledge.

✓ **Job Aspirations**

This variable analyzes whether male and female students have differing career aspirations and expectations, and how these are shaped by factors such as family support and household responsibilities.

d. Hypotheses Formulation

1. Hypothesis on Technology Access

Null Hypothesis (H_{01}): There is no significant difference in technology access between male and female students.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_{11}): Male students have significantly better access to technology than female students

2. Hypothesis on Academic Performance

Null Hypothesis (H_{02}): Gender disparity in technology access does not significantly affect the academic performance.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_{12}): Male students' better access to technology positively influences their academic performance compared to female students.

3. Hypothesis on Career Preparation

Null Hypothesis (H_{03}): Gender disparity of Technology access does not significantly affect the career preparation of male and female students.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_{13}): Male students' better access to technology significantly enhances their career preparation compared to female students.

4. Hypothesis on household responsibilities

Null Hypothesis (H_{03}): There is no significant association between household responsibilities and technology access among male and female undergraduate students.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_{13}): Female undergraduate students have significantly less access to technology than male students due to a higher burden of household responsibilities

5. Hypothesis on Family Support

Null Hypothesis (H_{09}): There is no significant relationship between family support and technology access among male and female undergraduate students.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_{10}): Female has less family support for education and further tech access than male students.

e. Survey and Interviews:

Questionnaires and interview guides were developed to address gender-based differences in technology access, academic performance, extracurricular involvement, household

responsibilities, and aspirations for future employment. The questions were designed to capture how these factors differentially affect male and female students.

f. Sample Selection:

A stratified sampling method was employed based on gender to facilitate a comparative analysis of male and female students' responses. Data were collected from both urban and rural educational institutions to ensure a broader and more comprehensive understanding of the research context.

g. Sample Size:

Given the large population of undergraduate students in Bangladesh, the standard sample size calculation for an infinite population was applied. A minimum of 385 responses is required for a 95% confidence level with a 5% margin of error. As 458 valid responses were obtained, the sample size is deemed sufficient for meaningful analysis.

h. Sampling Method:

A non-probability convenience sampling method was employed to gather responses from undergraduate students across Bangladesh. Efforts were made to ensure diversity in the sample by including participants from both rural and urban areas, from STEM and Non-STEM academic backgrounds, and across genders. Despite this diversity, the sample remains non-random, and therefore findings may not be fully generalizable to the entire undergraduate population.

i. Data Collection:

Primary data were collected through a structured survey questionnaire distributed via Google Forms. A total of 628 responses were initially received. All responses were compiled into an Excel spreadsheet for preliminary organization and review. During the data cleaning process, responses that were incomplete, irrelevant, or inconsistent with the study's objectives were removed, resulting in a final dataset of 458 valid responses for analysis.

In addition to the survey, semi-structured interviews were conducted with a subset of participants to gather qualitative insights, allowing a deeper understanding the gender gap in technology access and further academic preparation and career aspiration.

j. Statistical Analysis and Hypothesis Testing

To examine the relationships between gender and various indicators of technology access, academic performance, career preparation, household responsibilities, and family support, the study employed descriptive statistics, cross-tabulations, and Pearson's Chi-Square Test of Independence.

Cross-tabulation was used to present the frequency distributions of categorical variables across gender groups, enabling a comparative view of patterns and proportions. The Chi-Square test was applied to assess the statistical significance of associations between gender and each variable under investigation.

The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$ for all hypothesis tests. All analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics (Version 27).

5. Results

5.1. Demographic Information of Respondents

Table 1 : Demographic information of respondents

Category	Sub Category	Female	Male	Total
Gender		254	204	258
		55.5%	44.5%	100%
Age	18-20	29	24	53
		6.33%	5.24%	11.57%
	21-23	150	85	235
		32.75%	18.558%	51.3%
24-26	74	87	161	
	16.15%	18.99%	35.14%	
27 and above	1	8	9	
	0.2%	1.74%	1.94%	
Classified Study Field	STEM	63	86	149
		13.75%	18.77%	32.4%
	Non-STEM	190	118	308
	41.5%	25.7%	67.2%	
Unsure	1	0	1	
	0.4%	0%	0.4%	
Residential Area	Rural	68	71	139
		14.84%	15.5%	30.34%
	Urban	177	122	299
	38.64%	26.63%	65.27%	
Mofussil	9	11	20	
	1.96%	2.4%	4.36%	

Socioeconomic Status	High Income	5	5	10
		1%	1%	2%
	Middle Income	211	162	373
	46%	35.37%	81.44%	
Low Income	38	37	75	
	8.29%	8.07%	16.36%	

Undergrad Year	1 st Year	48 10.48%	38 8.29%	86 18.77%
	2 nd Year	39 8.51%	39 8.51%	78 17%
	3 rd Year	49 10.6%	43 9.38%	92 20%
	4 th Year	118 25.76%	84 18.34%	202 44.1%

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the 458 surveyed undergraduate students. Among the respondents, 254 (55.5%) were female, and 204 (44.5%) were male. The majority of participants (51.3%) were aged between 21 and 23 years. Approximately 44.1% were in the fourth year of their undergraduate studies. Regarding geographic background, 65.27% of the students were from urban areas, while 30.34% were from rural areas. In terms of academic discipline, 67.2% were enrolled in non-STEM fields. Additionally, 81.44% of the students reported coming from middle-income households.

5.2.Hypothesis on Technology Access

Table 2: Chi-Square Analysis of the Relationship between Gender and Technology Access

Test Variables	χ^2 Value	Df	Significance (2-sided)	Interpretation
Gender × Access to Personal Computer	57.349	1	<0.001	H ₀₁ is rejected
Gender × Tech usage for Education	3.472	3	0.324	Fail to reject H ₀₁
Gender × Challenges in accessing technology	12.051	3	0.007	H ₀₁ is rejected

Gender × Primary Study Devices	12.914	3	0.005	H ₀₁ is rejected
Gender × Device Acquisition Method	38.398	4	<0.001	H ₀₁ is rejected
Gender × Reason for Device Purchase	1.448	3	0.694	Fail to reject H ₀₁
Gender × Access to Multiple Devices for Studies	13.994	1	<0.001	H ₀₁ is rejected
Gender × Device Usage Time for Academics	7.344	4	0.119	Fail to reject H ₀₁
Gender × Device Giver	2.818	4	0.589	Fail to reject H ₀₁

Table 3 : Crosstab Summary of Gender and Technology Access

Variable	Category	Female (n/%)	Male (n/%)
Access to PC	Yes	94 37%	148 72.5%
	No	160 63%	56 27.5%
Technology Usage For Education	Daily(n/%)	193 76%	169 82.8%
	Weekly(n/%)	35 13.8%	22 10.8%
	Rarely(n/%)	20 7.9%	10 4.9%

	Never(n/%)	6 2.4%	3 1.5%
Challenges in Accessing Technology	Limited Knowledge of Technology	120 47.2%	68 33.3%
	Family Responsibilities	38 15%	27 13.2%
	Lack of Resources	59 23.2%	71 34.8%
	Other	37 14.6%	38 18.6%
Primary Device For Study	Smartphone	228 89.8%	164 80.4%
	Tablet	6 2.4%	9 4.4%
	Desktop	2 0.8%	12 5.9%
	Laptop	18 7.1%	19 9.3%
Device Acquisition Method	Purchased by me	48 18.9%	88 43.1%
	Purchased by a family member	176 69.3%	93 45.6%
	Received through Scholarship or Educational Program	3 1.2%	3 1.5%
	Gifted to Me	21 8.3%	20 9.8%
	Other	6 2.4%	0 0%
Reason for Device Purchase	For Personal Use	132 52%	96 47.1%
	For Educational Purposes	103 40.6%	90 44.1%
	For Work-Related Tasks	11 4.3%	12 5.9%
	Other	8 3.1%	6 2.9%

Access to Multiple Devices for Study	Yes	82 32.3%	101 49.5%
	No	172 67.7%	103 50.5%
Frequencies of Device Use for Academics	Daily	161 63.4%	136 66.7%
	Several Times A Week	52 20.5%	41 20.1%
	Rarely	14 5.5%	9 4.4%
	Occasionally	25 9.8%	11 5.4%
	Never	2 0.8%	7 3.4%
Device Giver	Parent/Guardian	191 75.2%	145 71.1%
	Sibling	23 9.1%	22 10.8%
	Friend	4 1.6%	6 2.9%
	Other	15 5.9%	9 4.4%
	Relative	21 8.3%	22 10.8%
Impact of Device Source on Technology Access	Yes	112 44.1%	104 51%
	No	142 55.9%	100 49%

These findings, as presented in Table 2 and Table 3, lead to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_{01}), confirming that there is a statistically significant gender gap in technology access. Male students consistently demonstrate better access to technological resources in terms of device ownership, diversity of study tools, and financial autonomy in acquiring devices. Conversely, female students face more challenges, including limited technological knowledge and family-related responsibilities.

5.3.Hypothesis on Academic Performance

Table 4 : Chi-Square Analysis of the Relationship Between Access to Technology and Weekly Hours Spent on Tuition or Extra Academic Support by Gender

Test Variables	Gender	χ^2 Value	Df	Significance (2-sided)	Interpretation
Access to Personal Computer × Weekly Hours Spent on Tuition or Academic Support × Gender Male/Female	Female	2.726	3	0.436	Fail to reject H ₀₃
	Male	1.516	3	0.679	
	Combined	1.661	3	0.646	
Frequency of Technology Use for Education × Weekly Hours Spent on Tuition or Academic Support × Gender Male/Female	Female	7.192	9	0.617	Fail to reject H ₀₃
	Male	8.665	9	0.469	
	Total	11.769	9	0.227	
Challenges in	Female	10.508	9	0.311	

Accessing Technology × Weekly Hours Spent on Tuition or Academic Support × Gender Male/Female	Male	18.824	9	0.027	Reject H ₀₃ (for male and total)
	Total	21.909	9	0.009	
Primary Study Devices × Weekly Hours Spent on Tuition or Academic Support × Gender Male/Female	Female	5.544	9	0.785	Reject H ₀₃ (for male and total)
	Male	17.502	9	0.041	
	Total	17.810	9	0.037	
Device Acquisition Method × Weekly Hours Spent on Tuition or Academic Support × Gender Male/Female	Female	20.332	12	0.061	Fail to reject H ₀
	Male	12.323	9	0.196	
	Total	14.442	12	0.273	

Reason for Device Purchase × Weekly Hours Spent on Tuition or Academic Support × Gender Male/Female	Female	9.884	9	0.360	Fail to reject H ₀
	Male	15.235	9	0.085	
	Total	9.307	9	0.409	
Access to Multiple Devices for Studies × Weekly Hours Spent on Tuition or Academic Support × Gender Male/Female	Female	10.445	3	0.015	Reject H ₀ (for Female only)
	Male	2.590	3	0.459	
	Total	4.345	3	0.227	
Frequency of Device Use for Academics × Weekly Hours Spent on Tuition or Academic Support × Gender Male/Female	Female	16.531	12	0.168	Fail to reject H ₀
	Male	8.408	12	0.752	
	Total	14.151	12	0.291	

Device Giver (If Gifted) × Weekly Hours Spent on Tuition or Academic Support × Gender Male/Female	Female	25.143	12	0.014	Reject H ₀ (for Female and Total)
	Male	15.656	12	0.207	
	Total	25.518	12	0.013	
Impact of Device Source on Technology Access × Weekly Hours Spent on Tuition or Academic Support × Gender Male/Female	Female	6.795	3	0.079	Fail to reject H ₀
	Male	0.890	3	0.828	
	Total	4.781	3	0.189	

Table 5 : Crosstab Summary of Technology Access (All Variables) and Academic Preparation (Weekly Hours Spent on Tuition or Extra Academic Support), Layered by Gender

Variable	Category	Gender		Weekly Study Hours (≤ 3 hours)		Weekly study Hours (≥ 10 hours)	
		Female (n/%)	Male (n/%)	Female (n/%)	Male (n/%)	Female (n/%)	Male (n/%)
Access to PC	Yes	94 37%	148 72.5%	50 53.2%	75 50.7%	6 6.4%	9 6.1%
	No	160 63%	56 27.5%	95 59.4%	25 44.6%	5 3.1%	6 10.7%
Technology Usage For Education	Daily(n/%)	193 76%	169 82.8%	104 53.9%	80 47.3%	9 4.7%	12 7.1%
	Weekly(n/%)	35 13.8%	22 10.8%	23 65.7%	12 54.5%	1 2.9%	1 4.5%
	Rarely(n/%)	20 7.9%	10 4.9%	14 70%	7 70%	0 0%	1 10%
	Never(n/%)	6 2.4%	3 1.5%	4 66.7%	1 33.3%	1 16.7%	1 33.3%
Challenges in Accessing Technology	Limited Knowledge of Technology	120 47.2%	68 33.3%	65 54.2%	28 41.2%	7 5.8%	9 13.2%
	Family Responsibilities	38 15%	27 13.2%	24 63.2%	16 59.3%	1 2.6%	3 11.1%
	Lack of Resources	49 23.2%	71 34.8%	29 49.2%	32 45.1%	2 3.4%	0 0%
	Other	37 16.6%	38 18.6%	27 73%	24 63.2%	1 2.7%	3 7.9%
Primary Device For Study	Smartphone	228 89.8%	164 80.4%	131 57.5%	84 51.2%	10 4.4%	13 7.9%
	Tablet	6 2.4%	9 4.4%	4 66.7%	3 33.3%	0 0%	2 22.2%
	Desktop	2 0.8%	12 5.9%	0 0%	2 16.7%	0 0%	0 0%
	Laptop	18 7.1%	19 9.3%	10 55.6%	11 57.9%	1 5.6%	0 0%
Device	Purchased by me	48	88	28	53	4	4

Acquisition Method		18.9%	43.1%	58.3%	60.2%	8.3%	4.5%
	Purchased by a family member	176 69.3%	93 45.6%	102 58%	36 38.7%	6 3.4%	8 8.6%
	Received through Scholarship or Educational Program	3 1.2%	3 1.5%	2 66.7%	1 33.3%	0 0%	0 0%
	Gifted to Me	21 8.3%	20 9.8%	8 38.1%	10 50%	0 0%	3 15%
	Other	6 2.4%	0 0%	5 83.3%	0 0%	1 16.7%	0 0%
Reason for Device Purchase	For Personal Use	132 52%	96 47.1%	77 58.3%	44 45.8%	5 3.8%	6 6.3%
	For Educational Purposes	103 40.6%	90 44.1%	61 59.2%	46 51.1%	3 2.9%	7 7.8%
	For Work-Related Tasks	11 4.3%	12 5.9%	4 36.4%	8 66.7%	2 18.2%	0 0%
	Other	8 3.1%	6 2.9%	3 37.5%	2 33.3%	1 12.5%	2 33.3%
Access to Multiple Devices for Study	Yes	82 32.3%	101 49.5%	49 59.8%	50 49.5%	8 9.8%	6 5.9%
	No	172 67.7%	103 50.5%	96 55.8%	50 48.5%	3 1.7%	9 8.7%
Frequencies of Device Use for Academics	Daily	161 63.4%	136 66.7%	90 55.9%	63 46.3%	8 5%	11 8.1%
	Several Times A Week	52 20.5%	41 20.1%	29 55.8%	21 51.2%	2 3.8%	2 4.9%
	Rarely	14 5.5%	9 4.4%	10 71.4%	4 44.4%	0 0%	1 11.1%
	Occasionally	25 9.8%	11 5.4%	15 60%	9 81.8%	0 0%	0 0%
	Never	2 0.8%	7 3.4%	1 50%	3 42.9%	1 50%	1 14.3%
Device Giver	Parent/Guardian	191 75.2%	145 71.1%	112 58.6%	74 51%	8 4.2%	9 6.2%
	Sibling	23 9.1%	22 10.8%	12 52.2%	12 54.5%	2 8.7%	1 4.5%
	Friend	4	6	4	1	0	0

		1.6%	2.9%	100%	16.7%	0%	0%
	Other	15 5.9%	9 4.4%	11 73.3%	5 55.6%	1 6.7%	2 22.2%
	Relative	21 8.3%	22 10.8%	6 28.6%	8 34.4%	0 0%	3 13.6%
Impact of Device Source on Technology Access	Yes	112 44.1%	104 51%	73 65.2%	51 49%	3 2.7%	8 7.7%
	No	142 55.9%	100 49%	72 50.7%	49 49%	8 5.6%	7 7%

As shown in Table 4 and Table 5, the null hypothesis (H_{03}) is partially rejected, indicating that gender-based disparities in technology access have a varied impact on academic performance. While certain factors, such as device type and acquisition method, significantly affect academic engagement for female students, others—like access challenges and primary study devices—are more influential for male students. These gender-specific patterns provide partial support for the alternative hypothesis (H_{04}).

5.4.Hypothesis on Career Preparation

Table 6 : Chi-Square Analysis of the Relationship Between Access to Technology and Part Time Job or Internship Experience by Gender

Test Variables	Gender	χ^2 Value	df	Significance (2-sided)	Interpretation
Access to Personal Computer \times Part-Time Job or Internship Experience \times Gender Male/Female	Female	20.734	1	<0.001	H ₀ is rejected (for female and total) Fail to reject (for mail)
	Male	1.314	1	0.252	
	Total	24.393	1	<0.001	
Frequency of Technology Use for	Female	7.636	3	0.054	Fail to reject H ₀

Education × Part-Time Job or Internship Experience × Gender Male/Female	Male	5.300	3	0.151	
	Total	5.060	3	0.167	
Challenges in Accessing Technology × Part-Time Job or Internship Experience × Gender Male/Female	Female	2.154	3	0.541	Fail to reject H ₀
	Male	4.769	3	0.190	
	Total	0.786	3	0.853	
Primary Study Devices × Part-Time Job or Internship Experience × Gender Male/Female	Female	11.935	3	0.008	H ₀ is rejected
	Male	9.395	3	0.024	
	Total	19.494	3	<0.001	
Device Acquisition Method × Part-Time Job or Internship Experience × Gender Male/Female	Female	4.746	4	0.314	Fail to reject H ₀₅ (for female , male) H ₀₅ is rejected (total)
	Male	6.041	3	0.110	
	Total	11.924	4	0.018	
Reason for Device Purchase × Part-Time Job or Internship Experience × Gender Male/Female	Female	0.904	3	0.825	H ₀₅ is rejected (male, total) Fail to reject (female)
	Male	10.961	3	0.012	

	Total	9.118	3	0.028	
Access to Multiple Devices for Studies × Part-Time Job or Internship Experience × Gender Male/Female	Female	13.046	1	<0.001	H ₀₅ is rejected
	Male	10.491	1	0.001	
	Total	27.875	1	<0.001	
Frequency of Device Use for Academics × Part-Time Job or Internship Experience × Gender Male/Female	Female	4.493	4	0.343	Fail to reject H ₀₅
	Male	0.248	4	0.993	
	Total	2.270	4	0.686	
Device Giver (If Gifted) × Part-Time Job or Internship Experience × Gender Male/Female	Female	2.639	4	0.620	Fail to reject H ₀₅ (female, total) H ₀₅ is rejected (male)
	Male	10.861	4	0.028	
	Total	2.913	4	0.573	
Impact of Device Source on Technology Access × Part-Time Job or Internship Experience × Gender Male/Female	Female	3.552	1	0.059	Fail to reject H ₀₅ (female) H ₀₅ is rejected (male, total)
	Male	18.480	1	<0.001	
	Total	20.496	1	<0.001	

Table 7 : Crosstab Summary of Technology Access Variables and Career preparation (Part time Job or Internship Experience) Layered by Gender

Variable	Category	Gender		Part time Job or Internship Experience	
		Female (n/%)	Male (n/%)	Female (n/%)	Male (n/%)
Access to PC	Yes	94 37%	148 72.5%	42 44.7%	66 46.6%
	No	160 63%	56 27.5%	29 18.1%	20 35.7%
Technology Usage For Education	Daily(n/%)	193 76%	169 82.8%	50 25.9%	76 45%
	Weekly(n/%)	35 13.8%	22 10.8%	16 45.7%	6 27.3%
	Rarely(n/%)	20 7.9%	10 4.9%	3 15%	2 20%
	Never(n/%)	6 2.4%	3 1.5%	2 33.3%	2 66.7%
Challenges in Accessing Technology	Limited Knowledge of Technology	120 47.2%	68 33.3%	29 24.2%	34 50%
	Family Responsibilities	38 15%	27 13.2%	12 31.6%	8 29.6%
	Lack of Resources	49 23.2%	71 34.8%	20 33.9%	26 36.6%
	Other	37 16.6%	38 18.6%	10 27%	18 47.4%
Primary Device For Study	Smartphone	228 89.8%	164 80.4%	57 25%	62 37.8%
	Tablet	6 2.4%	9 4.4%	3 50%	7 77.8%
	Desktop	2 0.8%	12 5.9%	2 100%	7 58.3%
	Laptop	18 7.1%	19 9.3%	9 50%	7 36.8%

Device Acquisition Method	Purchased by me	48 18.9%	88 43.1%	13 27.1%	45 51.1%
	Purchased by a family member	176 69.3%	93 45.6%	48 27.3%	31 33.3%
	Received through Scholarship or Educational Program	3 1.2%	3 1.5%	1 33.3%	1 33.3%
	Gifted to Me	21 8.3%	20 9.8%	9 42.9%	9 45%
	Other	6 2.4%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%
Reason for Device Purchase	For Personal Use	132 52%	96 47.1%	37 28%	44 45.8%
	For Educational Purposes	103 40.6%	90 44.1%	27 26.2%	29 32.2%
	For Work-Related Tasks	11 4.3%	12 5.9%	4 36.4%	9 75%
	Other	8 3.1%	6 2.9%	3 37.5%	4 66.7%
Access to Multiple Devices for Study	Yes	82 32.3%	101 49.5%	35 42.7%	54 53.5%
	No	172 67.7%	103 50.5%	36 20.9%	32 31.1%
Frequencies of Device Use for Academics	Daily	161 63.4%	136 66.7%	49 30.4%	58 42.6%
	Several Times A Week	52 20.5%	41 20.1%	15 28.8%	16 39%
	Rarely	14 5.5%	9 4.4%	1 7.1%	4 44.4%
	Occasionally	25 9.8%	11 5.4%	6 24%	5 45.5%
	Never	2 0.8%	7 3.4%	0 0%	3 42.9%
Device Giver	Parent/Guardian	191 75.2%	145 71.1%	56 29.3%	54 37.2%
	Sibling	23 9.1%	22 10.8%	7 30.4%	9 40.9%

	Friend	4 1.6%	6 2.9%	0 0%	5 83.3%
	Other	15 5.9%	9 4.4%	4 26.7%	7 77.8%
	Relative	21 8.3%	22 10.8%	4 19%	11 50%
Impact of Device Source on Technology Access	Yes	112 44.1%	104 51%	38 33.9%	59 56.7%
	No	142 55.9%	100 49%	33 23.2%	27 27%

Table 8 : Chi-Square Analysis of Technology access (Frequency of Technology Access for Education) and Confidence in Entering Job Market by Gender

Test Variables	Gender	χ^2 Value	Df	Significance (2-sided)
Confidence in entering job market after graduation	Female	12.079	9	0.209
	Male	60.645	9	<0.001

Table 9 : Crosstab Summary of Technology Access (Frequency of Technology Access for Education) and Confidence in entering job market after graduation, Layered by Gender

Confidence in entering job market	Frequency of tech use for education	Female	Male
Very Confident	Daily	33 67.3%	55 90.2%
	Weekly	10 20.4%	4 6.6%
	Rarely	3 6.1%	2 3.3%
	Never	3 6.1%	0 0%
Confident	Daily	94 77.7%	74 83.1%
	Weekly	18	12

		14.9%	13.5%
	Rarely	9 7.4%	3 3.4%
	Never	0 0%	0 0%
Neutral	Daily	55 79.7%	33 76.7%
	Weekly	6 8.7%	5 11.6%
	Rarely	6 8.7%	5 11.6%
	Never	2 2.9%	0 0%
Not Confident	Daily	11 73.3%	7 63.6%
	Weekly	1 6.7%	1 9.1%
	Rarely	2 13.3%	0 0%
	Never	1 6.7%	3 27.3%

Table 10: Chi-Square Analysis of Career Goal after Postgrad and Technology Access (Frequency of Technology use) by Gender

Test Variables	Gender	χ^2 Value	Df	Significance (2-sided)
Career Goal After Postgrad \times Frequency of Tech use	Female	13.444	6	0.037
	Male	15.858	6	0.015

Table 11: Crosstab Summary of Career Goal after Postgrad and Frequency of Technology Use for Education, Layered by Gender

Career Goal after postgrad	Frequency of tech use for education	Female (n/%)	Male (n/%)
STEM field	Daily	54 91.5%	65 90.3%

	Weekly	4 6.8%	6 8.3%
	Rarely	0 0%	1 1.4%
	Never	1 1.7%	0 0%
Non-STEM field	Daily	115 71.4%	86 78.2%
	Weekly	26 16.1%	15 13.6%
	Rarely	17 10.6%	8 7.3%
	Never	3 1.9%	1 0.9%
Unsure	Daily	24 70.6%	18 81.8%
	Weekly	5 14.7%	1 4.5%
	Rarely	3 8.8%	1 4.5%
	Never	2 5.9%	2 9.1%

The chi-square tests (Table 6, 8, 10) show that gender disparities in technology access significantly affect career preparation. Male students have better access to technology (personal computers, multiple devices, advanced devices) and higher independence in device ownership, which correlates with greater participation in internships, STEM activities, and higher confidence in entering the job market. Female students face more access-related barriers impacting career readiness, and their confidence is less linked to technology use. Frequent technology use strongly associates with STEM engagement and clearer career goals, with males exhibiting slightly stronger patterns. Overall, male students' superior technology access enhances their career preparation and confidence more than females.

5.5.Hypothesis on Household Responsibilities

Table 12 : Chi-Square Analysis of Technology Access (Frequency of Technology Access for Education) and Weekly Hours on Household Responsibilities by Gender

Test Variables	Gender	χ^2 Value	Df	Significance (2-sided)	Interpretation
frequency of tech access for education × weekly hours on household responsibilities	Female	2.707	4	0.608	Fail to reject H0
	Male	9.693	4	0.046	H0 is rejected
	Total	8.399	4	0.078	Fail to reject H0

Table 13: Crosstab Summary of Household Responsibilities (weekly hours) and Tech Access (Frequency of Tech Access for Education), Layered by Gender

Variables	Frequency of tech use for education	Daily		Weekly		Rarely	
		Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male
Weekly Hours Spent On Household Responsibilities							
Low		86 76.8%	81 91%	15 13.4%	5 5.6%	11 9.8%	3 3.4%
Moderate		74 71.8%	60 73.2%	17 16.5%	14 17.1%	12 11.7%	8 9.8%
High		33 84.6%	28 84.8%	3 7.7%	3 9.1%	3 7.7%	2 6.1%

No significant association exists between household responsibilities and technology access for female students ($p=0.608$), but a significant link is found for males ($p=0.046$). Overall, the association is not significant ($p=0.078$). Females show a greater decrease in daily tech use as household duties increase, though high-responsibility females still have high tech access. This suggests household responsibilities may reduce female tech access, but the evidence is inconclusive.

5.6.Hypothesis on Family Support

Table 14 : Chi-Square Analysis of Technology Access (Frequency of Technology Access for Education) and Family Support for Education by Gender

Test Variables	Gender	χ^2 Value	Df	Significance (2-sided)	Interpretation
frequency of tech access for education \times Family Support for Education	Female	2.660	2	0.265	Fail to reject H0
	Male	5.733	2	0.057	Fail to reject H0
	Total	1.472	2	0.479	Fail to reject H0

Table 15 : Crosstab Summary of Frequency of Tech Use for Education and Family Support, Layered by Gender

Variables	Frequency of tech use for education	Daily		Weekly		Rarely	
		Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male
Family Support for Education							
Yes		180 93.3%	154 91.1%	33 94.3%	17 77.3%	22 84.6%	13 100%
No		13 6.7%	15 8.9%	2 5.7%	5 22.7%	4 15.4%	0 0%

No significant overall association between family support and technology access was observed ($p = .479$). While females showed no significant relationship ($p = .265$), the association for males approached significance ($p = .057$) but was limited by low expected counts. Crosstab results indicate that family support markedly increases daily technology use for education (females 93.3%, males 91.1% vs. without support: females 6.7%, males 8.9%), underscoring its critical role, with females exhibiting marginally higher usage.

6. Discussion

6.1. Interpretation of Demographic Trends

The study surveyed a total of 458 undergraduate students to examine the gender gap in education and its impact on job market preparedness. Among the respondents, 254 were female (55.5%) and 204 were male (44.5%), indicating a higher representation of female students in the sample.

Among the 458 respondents, the largest group falls within the 21-23 age range (51.3%), followed by those aged 24-26 (35.14%). Participants aged 18-20 make up 11.57%, while only 1.94% are 27 years or older. This distribution represents a typical undergraduate demographic, providing a relevant basis for analyzing education and job market preparedness.

The distribution of undergraduate students across different academic years shows that the majority are in their 4th year (44.1%), followed by 3rd-year students (20%). 1st-year and 2nd-year students make up 18.77% and 17%, respectively. This breakdown highlights a higher representation of senior students in the sample, which may provide deeper insights into their preparedness for the job market.

The data on respondents' current residential areas shows that the majority reside in urban areas (65.27%), while 30.34% live in rural areas. A smaller portion, 4.36%, are from mofussil regions. This distribution highlights the predominance of urban residents in the sample.

The distribution of respondents by field of study indicates that 67.2% are enrolled in non-STEM disciplines, while 32.4% are pursuing STEM fields. Only 0.4% of respondents were unsure about their field of study. This data reflects a higher representation of non-STEM students in the sample.

The majority of respondents (81.44%) come from middle-income families, while 16.36% belong to low-income groups, and only 2% are from high-income backgrounds. This indicates that most participants have moderate financial resources, potentially influencing their access to opportunities.

6.2.Results Interpretation: Technology Access

Hypothesis on Technology Access

Null Hypothesis (H_{01}): There is no significant difference in technology access between male and female students.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_{02}): Male students have significantly better access to technology than female students

According to Table-2, The chi-square tests reveal significant gender differences in several aspects of technology access. Specifically, access to personal computers ($\chi^2 = 57.349$, $p < 0.001$), challenges in accessing technology ($\chi^2 = 12.051$, $p = 0.007$), primary study devices ($\chi^2 = 12.914$, $p = 0.005$), device acquisition method ($\chi^2 = 38.398$, $p < 0.001$), and access to multiple study devices ($\chi^2 = 13.994$, $p < 0.001$) show statistically significant differences between male and female students.

According to Table 3, notable gender disparities exist in several aspects of technology access. Access to personal computers is significantly higher between males (72.5%) compared to only 37% of females, highlighting a substantial gap in computer availability. Besides, most female students (89.8%) primarily rely on smartphones for their studies, whereas male students demonstrate a more diversified usage of desktops, laptops, and tablets, indicating a stronger digital infrastructure among males. In terms of device acquisition, a significantly higher percentage of male students (43.1%) purchased their own devices compared to only 18.9% of females, most of whom depend on family purchases. This indicates that male students tend to have greater financial independence or access to financial support. Additionally, 49.5% of male students use multiple devices, compared to just 32.3% of females, suggesting a broader exposure to and flexibility with technology. When it comes to challenges in accessing technology, female students more frequently reported limited technological knowledge (47.2%) and family responsibilities (15%) as barriers, whereas male students more often cited a lack of resources (34.8%). These findings reflect underlying gendered social roles and expectations that shape students' access to and use of technology.

6.3 Result Interpretation : Academic Preparation

Hypothesis on Academic Performance

Null Hypothesis (H_{03}): Gender disparity in technology access does not significantly affect the academic performance.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_{04}): Male students' better access to technology positively influences their academic performance compared to female students.

Note: Academic preparation related variables are weekly study hours, involvement in extra-curricular activities, enrollment on tuition or extra academic support, weekly hours on extra academic support (most imp indicators), impact of part time on academic preparation, experience or witnessing of gender based discrimination in academic, access to edu resource. Among them weekly hours spent on tuition or extra academic support is considered as the most important indicators. To make statistical analysis simple and perceivable this academic preparation related variable is being picked. Furthermore rather than obtained GPA or academic grade study hours, academic efforts and practices are being considered.

The statistical analysis of the second hypothesis aimed to examine whether gender-based disparities in technology access significantly influence academic performance. Chi-square tests (Table 4) were conducted across multiple variables related to technology usage and academic engagement, disaggregated by gender. The null hypothesis was rejected in several cases, indicating significant associations. For instance, the challenges in accessing technology and the primary study devices used showed statistically significant relationships with academic support

time for male students and in the overall dataset, but not for females. In contrast, the access to multiple devices and the identity of the device giver (if gifted) were significantly associated with academic support time for female students and in the overall group, but not for males. These results suggest that different aspects of technology access affect academic outcomes differently for male and female students. Overall, while many associations were not statistically significant, a few key factors demonstrated meaningful gender-specific impacts on academic engagement, partially supporting the alternative hypothesis.

The crosstab summary (Table 5) provides consistent evidence supporting the alternative hypothesis that male students' better access to technology positively influences their academic performance compared to female students.

First, a higher percentage of male students (72.5%) report having access to a personal computer than female students (37%), suggesting a significant gender gap in essential educational technology. Among those who study for ≥ 10 hours weekly, the proportion of males with PC access (6.1%) is slightly higher than females (6.4%), but more pronounced in the moderate study group (≤ 3 hours), where male PC access (50.7%) exceeds that of females (53.2%), showing that females with PCs are slightly more represented only in the lower study-hour bracket.

Daily educational use of technology is slightly higher among males (82.8%) compared to females (76%), and this consistent daily engagement is likely contributing to improved academic preparation. Weekly and rare users are more commonly female, with 13.8% and 7.9% respectively, while the corresponding percentages for males are lower, suggesting that females experience more irregular technology use for academic purposes.

Challenges in accessing technology also disproportionately affect females. Limited knowledge of technology is more common among female students (47.2%) than males (33.3%), and “lack of resources” is cited more frequently by males (34.8%) than females (23.2%), indicating that while both genders face access issues, the nature of those barriers differs—with females experiencing more knowledge-related and family burden barriers.

Male students show greater access to multiple devices (49.5% vs. 32.3%), which can enhance learning flexibility and efficiency. Furthermore, daily device use for academic purposes is higher among males (66.7%) compared to females (63.4%), and the percentage of females who rarely or never use devices for academic work is slightly higher, indicating less consistency in engagement.

Device acquisition patterns also reveal that a larger share of male students purchase their own devices (43.1%) compared to females (18.9%), demonstrating a level of autonomy that may lead to more consistent and purposeful use. Meanwhile, female students are more dependent on family members, which may limit timely access and control over devices.

Overall, male students consistently show better access, more frequent use, and fewer challenges in using technology for academic purposes. These advantages correlate with a higher presence in more academically engaged study brackets (e.g., ≥ 10 study hours), providing reasonable support for the alternative hypothesis.

6.4 Result Interpretation : Career Preparation

Hypothesis on Career Preparation

Null Hypothesis (H_{05}): Gender disparity of Technology access does not significantly affect the career preparation of male and female students.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_{06}): Male students' better access to technology significantly enhances their career preparation compared to female students.

The variables related to career preparation include career goals after post-graduation, involvement in extracurricular activities, participation in STEM-related extracurricular activities, part-time job or internship experience during studies, confidence in entering the job market, current enrollment in tuition classes or extra academic support sessions, challenges in balancing studies with tuition or part-time work, perceived impact of tuition or part-time work on academic performance, and motivation to engage in such work. Among these, career goals after post-graduation, participation in STEM-related extracurricular activities, part-time or internship experience during studies, and confidence in entering the job market were identified as the most significant indicators of career preparation during the study period. Initially, a Chi-Square test was conducted to examine the association between all technology access variables and the most critical career preparation indicator, part-time job or internship experience, to determine the influence of technology access on this aspect of career development. To streamline the analysis, the variable 'Frequency of Access to Technology for Educational Purposes' was later selected as the primary focus.

The chi-square test results (Table 6) reveal that in several key areas, such as access to personal computers, use of multiple devices, primary study devices, and the impact of device sources, H_{05} is rejected, indicating a significant relationship between gender-based technology access and career preparation. Specifically, female students show more significant associations in access-related barriers affecting their ability to pursue part-time jobs or internships. In contrast, many variables for male students fail to reject H_{05} , implying their better access may not hinder career preparation. Overall, the findings support the alternative hypothesis (H_{06}) that male students' better access to technology significantly enhances their career preparation compared to female students.

According to Table 7, the crosstab data supports the alternative hypothesis (H_{06}), indicating that male students' better access to technology significantly enhances their career preparation compared to female students. A higher percentage of males (72.5%) had access to personal computers compared to females (37%), and among them, a greater proportion engaged in part-time jobs or internships (46.6% vs. 44.7%). Males also reported more frequent daily use of technology for education (82.8% vs. 76%) and greater access to multiple devices (49.5% vs. 32.3%). Furthermore, males had better access to advanced study devices like laptops and desktops, which were associated with higher participation in internships. The data also shows that a significant number of males purchased devices themselves (43.1%) compared to females (18.9%), suggesting greater autonomy and readiness for career-related tasks. These patterns consistently show that better access to and control over technology among male students correlates with improved career preparation outcomes.

To streamline the analysis, only the variable representing the frequency of technology access for educational purposes was selected from the broader set of technology access indicators.

The data reveals a gender-based pattern in the relationship between frequency of technology use and participation in STEM extracurricular activities. Among females, daily technology users showed the highest level of STEM participation, with 58 individuals (80.6%) involved, while a smaller proportion (74.2%) of daily users who did not participate in STEM activities was observed. Similarly, 92 males who used technology daily (90.2%) participated in STEM extracurriculars, slightly higher than the 75.5% who did not. For weekly users, STEM participation dropped sharply: only 13.9% of females and 4.9% of males reported participating in STEM activities. This downward trend continued among those who rarely or never used technology, where STEM participation was minimal in both genders (females: 2.8% and 2.8%; males: 2.9% and 2%, respectively). Overall, the results indicate a positive association between frequent technology use and STEM engagement, with males showing slightly higher STEM involvement at the daily usage level.

Based on the crosstab summary (Table 9) and the chi-square test results (Table 8), we can analyze the relationship among technology access, gender, and confidence in entering the job market after graduation. Based on the chi-square results ($\chi^2 = 60.645$, $df = 9$, $p < 0.001$), the null hypothesis is rejected for male students, indicating a statistically significant relationship between the frequency of technology use and their confidence in entering the job market. On the other hand we fail to reject the null hypothesis ($\chi^2 = 12.079$, $df = 9$, $p = 0.209$) for female students, showing no statistically significant relationship between the frequency of technology use and their confidence in entering the job market.

The majority of male students who use technology daily report being "Very Confident" (90.2%), with confidence decreasing as the frequency of technology use decreases. This suggests that

male students who have more access to technology feel more confident about entering the job market after graduation.

On the other hand, the confidence levels for female students do not show as clear a pattern based on technology use. For example, a significant portion of female students who use technology daily are "Confident" (77.7%), but the pattern does not follow the same trend seen with male students.

Therefore, male students' better access to technology plays a critical role in enhancing their confidence in career readiness, while for female students, other factors might be influencing their career confidence.

The Chi-square tests of Table 10, reveal a statistically significant association between students' career goals after post-graduation and their frequency of technology use for education, with significance levels of $p = 0.037$ for females and $p = 0.015$ for males. This suggests that for both genders, how frequently students use technology is meaningfully related to whether they aim for STEM careers, non-STEM careers, or are still unsure.

The crosstab data of Table 11 shows that among students aiming for a STEM career, a very high proportion use technology daily—91.5% of females and 90.3% of males. Technology use decreases noticeably among those with non-STEM goals, with 71.4% of females and 78.2% of males using it daily. Among those unsure about their career goals, 70.6% of females and 81.8% of males also report daily technology use, though at slightly lower rates than those pursuing STEM.

Weekly, rarely, and never usage categories are more prominent among students pursuing non-STEM or unsure paths, especially for females—16.1% of non-STEM females use tech weekly, and 10.6% use it rarely. For males in the non-STEM group, 13.6% use it weekly and 7.3% rarely. These patterns suggest that more frequent technology use correlates with a stronger orientation toward STEM careers, and this relationship is slightly stronger for males, as indicated by their lower p-value.

6.5 Result Interpretation : Household Responsibilities

Hypothesis on household responsibilities

Null Hypothesis (H_{07}): There is no significant association between household responsibilities and technology access among male and female undergraduate students.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_{08}): Female undergraduate students have significantly less access to technology than male students due to a higher burden of household responsibilities

The Chi-square analysis (Table 12) did not find a significant association between household responsibilities and technology access among female undergraduate students ($p = 0.608$). However, a significant association was found among males ($p = 0.046$), suggesting that for male students, tech access may vary based on household responsibility levels. Overall, the relationship was not statistically significant when considering both genders together ($p = 0.078$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is partially supported—gender-specific factors may influence the association differently.

The crosstab analysis (Table 13) reveals a noticeable trend in the relationship between household responsibilities and technology access for educational purposes, particularly across gender lines. Among students with low household responsibilities, a higher proportion of male students (91%) reported daily tech use compared to female students (76.8%). As household responsibilities increase, the proportion of daily tech use decreases more markedly among females than males, with more females falling into the weekly and rarely access categories. While both male and female students with high responsibilities still report high daily access rates (84.6% and 84.8% respectively), the shift in access frequency among females across the categories suggests a potential impact of household duties on their tech usage. These results imply that while female students may experience a reduction in tech access with increased household burden, the evidence is not strong enough to confirm a statistically significant relationship.

6.6 Result Interpretation : Family Support

Hypothesis on Family Support

Null Hypothesis (H_{09}): There is no significant relationship between family support and technology access among male and female undergraduate students.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_{10}): Female has less family support for education and further tech access than male students.

To examine the association between family support and technology access among male and female students, a chi-square test (Table 14) was performed after collapsing the family support variable into two categories: “Yes/Partially” and “No.” For the total sample, no significant association was found, $\chi^2(2, N = 458) = 1.472, p = .479$. Gender-specific analysis also showed no

statistically significant association for females, $\chi^2(2, N = 254) = 2.660, p = .265$, while the result for males approached significance, $\chi^2(2, N = 204) = 5.733, p = .057$. However, assumptions of the chi-square test were partially violated, as 33.3% of the cells had expected counts below 5, which may affect the robustness of the findings. This limitation should be considered when interpreting the near-significant result for male students, which could suggest a possible link between lack of family support and limited access to technology.

The crosstab analysis (Table 15) of technology access and family support across gender reveals a consistent pattern: students with family support report significantly higher use of technology for educational purposes, regardless of gender. Among females with family support, 93.3% use technology daily, 94.3% weekly, and 84.6% rarely. Similarly, males with support show high usage—91.1% daily, 77.3% weekly, and 100% rarely. In contrast, those without family support demonstrate notably lower access. Only 6.7% of females and 8.9% of males without support use technology daily. The weekly usage drops further among unsupported males (22.7%) compared to females (5.7%), and rare usage is lowest among unsupported females (15.4%) while no unsupported males reported rare use. This suggests that family support plays a crucial role in facilitating consistent access to educational technology, with females generally showing slightly higher access rates than males across all frequency categories.

7. Conclusion

In conclusion, while statistical significance varies across the tested hypotheses, a clear and concerning pattern emerges: gender-based disparities in educational technology access are not only present but are also deeply linked with broader socio-cultural and economic inequities. Male students benefit from greater access to multiple digital devices, higher financial independence in acquiring technology, and more consistent usage patterns—all of which are positively associated with academic engagement, participation in STEM fields, and increased confidence in entering the job market.

In contrast, female students face a host of structural barriers. These include a heavier reliance on family for technology access, limited exposure to multiple devices, and the compounding effects of household responsibilities. Although daily technology use improves their STEM career aspirations, it does not significantly enhance their career confidence—suggesting that digital access alone cannot overcome entrenched gender norms. Notably, certain chi-square tests—such as those examining family support for male students—violate core assumptions (e.g., over 33% of expected cell counts are below 5), which limits the reliability and generalizability of the statistical significance. These findings should therefore be interpreted with caution, particularly in policy formulation.

The results underscore an urgent need for gender-responsive policy interventions. Educational institutions and governments should consider implementing subsidized laptop or device programs targeted at female students, digital literacy workshops to increase usage confidence, and institutional support systems that account for domestic burdens. These measures can help shift the current digital imbalance and empower all students, regardless of gender, to fully benefit from the educational opportunities of the digital age.

8. Limitation of The Research

While this study provides valuable insights into gender disparities in technology access and their implications for academic and career readiness among undergraduate students in Bangladesh, it is not without limitations. First, out of the 628 responses initially collected, only 458 were retained after data cleaning due to incomplete or inconsistent entries. Although the final sample remains statistically valid, this reduction may affect the overall representativeness of the findings. Second, the study did not include Grade Point Average (GPA) data as a measure of academic achievement. Instead, it emphasized academic effort indicators such as study hours and engagement with educational technology. The exclusion of GPA may limit the ability to draw direct conclusions about academic performance outcomes. Third, to maintain focus and simplicity, only a limited number of variables were selected to represent academic and career readiness. This narrower scope, while deliberate, may not fully capture the complexity and multidimensional nature of student preparedness. Future research should consider incorporating a wider range of indicators and more comprehensive performance metrics to enhance the depth and generalizability of findings.

Bibliography

Ahmed, R., & Hyndman-Rizk, N. (2020). The higher education paradox: Towards improving women's empowerment, agency development and labour force participation in Bangladesh. *Gender and Education*, 32(4), 447–465. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09540253.2018.1471452>

Alam, G. M., & Forhad, M. A. R. (2023). The Impact of Accessing Education via Smartphone Technology on Education Disparity—A Sustainable Education Perspective. *Sustainability*, 15(14), Article 14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151410979>

Chan, K., Spaid Miedema, S., Naved, R. T., & Yount, K. M. (2023). Beyond Girls' Education: Pathways to Women's Post-Marital Education in Matlab, Bangladesh. *Feminist Economics*, 29(1), 38–69. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13545701.2022.2082510>

- Hossain, M. A., & Tisdell, C. A. (2005). Closing the gender gap in Bangladesh: Inequality in education, employment and earnings. *International Journal of Social Economics*, 32(5), 439–453. <https://doi.org/10.1108/03068290510591281>
- Hossain, Md. T., Akter, S., Nishu, N. A., Khan, L., Shuha, T. T., Jahan, N., Rahman, M. M., & Khatun, Mst. T. (2023). The gender divide in digital competence: A cross-sectional study on university students in southwestern Bangladesh. *Frontiers in Education*, 8, 1258447. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2023.1258447>
- Islam, Md. A. (2022). Industry 4.0: Skill set for employability. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 6(1), 100280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2022.100280>
- Islam, N., & Jirattikorn, A. (2024). Breaking gender barriers in STEM education for achieving the SDG of quality education in Bangladesh. *Development in Practice*, 34(1), 129–135. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09614524.2023.2229965>
- Jamatia, P. L. (2023). The Impact of Parental Economic Challenges on Women's Education in India. *Journal of Women Empowerment and Studies*, 3(05), Article 05. <https://doi.org/10.55529/jwes.35.10.19>
- Kuteesa, K. N., Akpuokwe, C. U., & Udeh, C. A. (2024). GENDER EQUITY IN EDUCATION: ADDRESSING CHALLENGES AND PROMOTING OPPORTUNITIES FOR SOCIAL EMPOWERMENT. *International Journal of Applied Research in Social Sciences*, 6(4), Article 4. <https://doi.org/10.51594/ijarss.v6i4.1034>
- Mariscal, J., Mayne, G., Aneja, U., & Sorgner, A. (2019). Bridging the Gender Digital Gap. *Economics*, 13(1), 20190009. <https://doi.org/10.5018/economics-ejournal.ja.2019-9>
- Moniruzzaman, Md., & Emran, S. J. (2021). Education and Inequality in Rural Bangladesh: A Longitudinal Study. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Rural Development*, 31(1), 37–61. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10185291211010867>
- Nabizada, S., Quraishi, T., Sadat, R., Kirmani, A., Hashemi, Z., Haidari, N., & Faramarz, N. (2024). Transforming Afghanistan: Enhancing Technology Access to Overcome Gender Discrimination. *APLIKATIF: Journal of Research Trends in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 3(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.59110/aplikatif.v3i1.344>
- Pulatovna, N. G. (2024). OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES FOR WOMEN IN THE DIGITAL AGE. *Frontline Social Sciences and History Journal*, 4(05), Article 05. <https://doi.org/10.37547/social-fsshj-04-05-05>
- Rahman, P. (2024). A reflexive thematic analysis exploring the experiences of undergraduate women in STEM in Bangladesh. *Discover Education*, 3(1), 111. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44217-024-00185-9>

Sarkar, R. K. (2022). *Socio cultural barriers of girls' educational attainment: Experiences from rural Bangladesh*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6789192>

Šestić, M., Rahimić, Z., Bičo Ćar, M., & Hodžić, D. (2020). Global Gender Gap Index: Is It Time to Measure Technology Access Gap Also? In I. Karabegović (Ed.), *New Technologies, Development and Application III* (pp. 924–929). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-46817-0_104

Siddiky, M. R., & Akter, S. (2021). The students' career choice and job preparedness strategies: A social environmental perspective. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, 10(2), Article 2. <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijere.v10i2.21086>

Smith, D. (2015). Does Gender Matter? University Library Access and Career Preparedness. *Online Learning*, 19(4). <https://doi.org/10.24059/olj.v19i4.554>

Tasmin, M., Ahmed, N., & Motahar, T. (2019). Gender Disparity in Computer Science Education in Bangladesh: A Study of Women's Participation in Computer Science. *2019 IEEE International Conference on Engineering, Technology and Education (TALE)*, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TALE48000.2019.9225981>

Valli, Dr. V. A. (2025). Women and Technology: Bridging the Digital Divide. *Indospace Publications*, 09(01), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.55041/ijsrem40877>